

ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8147926>

Abstract. *The results of the assessment of the digital competence of the future elementary school teachers presented in the study are used for planning the modernization of the content of educational subjects related to the use of information and communication technologies in teaching, developing continuous education and training programs. is of practical importance in output.*

Keywords: *future primary school teachers, digital competence, information and communication technologies, continuous education.*

The results of the assessment of the digital competence of the future elementary school teachers presented in the study are practical in planning the modernization of the content of educational subjects related to the use of information and communication technologies in teaching, in the development of continuous education and educational programs. is important. They identify problem areas and allow to critically examine the actions of future elementary school teachers in various pedagogical situations, to evaluate the rationality of choosing and using digital tools and services to solve pedagogical problems.

Formation of digital competences of future primary school teachers can be done in the following ways:

- continuous self-education and professional development using Internet technologies, participation in webinars and master classes;
- provision of a methodical support system by the school;
- participation in professional skill contests, methodical development contests, science and digital competence improvement and identification tests;
- creating a website or blog for information, future elementary school teachers and their parents, colleagues, etc.;
- development of cloud technologies, creation and use of science and elective courses or providing access to working materials through Internet services.

In our research, we considered the process of distance education as a form of using modern and popular information communication technologies to organize interactive communication in education.

An important condition for the organization of distance education is that the interacting parties have a personal computer and the global Internet, but this is not enough. In the process of distance education, dialog communication cannot be built without interactive programs and additional software. It is precisely because of the insufficient skills of students to work with the

components of the distance learning process that problems have arisen in many educational institutions[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

The study showed that 25% of the prospective elementary school teachers who participated in the survey did not use Internet resources, messengers and software in the process of distance education, because they did not have the skills to work with these forms. they don't have.

Educational platforms not only made it possible to organize the distance education process of future elementary school teachers, make it effective, but also to improve the skills of future elementary school teachers in information and communication technologies. With the help of these resources, free webinars, video lectures and workshops were held for future elementary teachers, which helped to improve their digital competence. Thus, the development of digital competences of modern future elementary school teachers is one of the main tasks, which can be solved by continuous self-education of future elementary school teachers, professional knowledge and related to improving skills.

Digital technologies make it much easier to provide teaching material to future elementary teachers, which allows for a significant extension of learning.

Multimedia resources are the most effective e-learning resources. The convenience of this type of resource is that educational information can be presented in a variety of ways: using text, graphics, photos, video, sound, and animation. Based on the above, we see the need for this source [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**] :

- uses all types of perception, respectively, all types of student's thinking and practical activities are established. The process of providing information to students through the use of information technologies makes this process active due to the novelty of this form of work, and also makes it bright and colorful with the help of multimedia files;

- the educational process is individualized through tasks of different levels, by mastering the material in an individual form.

The advantages of information technology in education include:

- due to the individuality of each student, using a convenient way of perceiving information, which later forms positive educational ideas;

- increasing students' independence in answering questions;

- improvement of one's performance due to feedback, which subsequently leads to improvement of self-control skills;

- to carry out independent research work that develops creative activity (creating construction works, modeling, making presentations).

Future elementary school teachers are recommended to use presentations to check the correctness of tasks, because a lot of time is spent on reproducing graphs and drawings, explaining tasks that lead to difficulties. In other words, e-learning technologies imply independent learning of the material. In this case, the teacher acts as a consultant, an assistant who explains unclear questions if necessary.

The main advantages of digitization are:

- independence, since digital skills imply independent work, a desire for knowledge arises; future elementary school teachers will achieve great success without excessive teacher care;

- E-learning allows you to get rid of paperwork: all textbooks are available on a computer, and a tablet can easily replace workbooks;

- economy; we are talking about office equipment, electronic gadgets and computers require replacement only in case of damage;

- simplification of teacher's work; In e-learning, the teacher works more as an assistant, who determines the direction of movement of future elementary teachers. They can independently seek knowledge through digital skills;

- a step into the future, implies rapid adaptation to the world of constantly developing technology, helps to better guide in the field of information technologies in the future.

In addition to the advantages of digital technologies, there are also disadvantages of the modern information education system. In this case, we must consider the risk of a negative outcome. This system is being used for the first time, we have no practice, and therefore we have nothing to compare it to. We cannot say with absolute certainty about the effectiveness of this innovation. These can be:

Lack of creativity. Information technologies do not provide opportunities for self-expression. Electronic fragments are emotionless in nature. Scientists have proven that creating a color scheme and notes in a notebook helps to remember information better, which in turn develops creativity.

Weakening of mental abilities. We can already observe this phenomenon, because it is enough to go online to search for a question of interest and get the necessary information. In the modern world of information technology, a person does not need independent thinking, the global network does everything for him, which in turn leads to a weakening of mental abilities.

Poor socialization. Prospective primary school teachers are less likely to see familiar people in the digital world. He finds himself in another society where he does not know anyone. In an educational institution, he not only gets knowledge, but also communicates with society, communicates with his friends. Digital technologies significantly weaken the level of socialization of a person, which can negatively affect the development of a person in the future.

Problems of physical development. Staying in front of the computer screen for a long time leads to eye fatigue and then deterioration of vision. Visual fine motor skills suffer first. Keyboard work can change the physiology of the fingers, resulting in changes in the structure of bones, joints and muscles.

Full control. Absolute control belongs to teachers, future elementary school teachers and parents, as a personal case is opened for each of them, detailed information about each family member is collected. If a child gets a bad grade, parents know about it and hide the diary and do not tell about what they got.

There is no bad grade. This gives a blow to independence, when problems arise, children try to solve them independently, albeit in the wrong ways.

The task of teachers. After the full implementation of digital technologies in the field of education, experts will be replaced by robots and virtual systems, which in turn will lead to the loss of teachers' jobs.

So, summarizing the above, we come to the conclusion that, despite the apparent absolute perfection and effectiveness of the e-learning system, there are also negative aspects. It is impossible not to highlight the negative impact of digitization on health and physical development. We believe that digital technologies should be used in education in such a way that they do not harm anyone. The ideal formula for effective teaching: digital technologies and elementary teachers is a tandem.

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